

Emergent spatial patterns can indicate upcoming regime shifts in a realistic model of coral community - Supplement 1: Model parametrization

Alexandre Génin^{*1,2}, Sergio A. Navarrete^{2,3,4}, Angeles Garcia-Mayor^{1,5}, Evie A. Wiers²

The American Naturalist

1 Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University, PO Box 80115, 3508 TC, Utrecht, The Netherlands.

2 Estación Costera de Investigaciones Marinas and Millenium Nucleus for Ecology and Conservation of Temperate Mesophotic, Reefs Ecosystems (NUTME), Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Las Cruces, Chile.

3 Center for Applied Ecology and Sustainability (CAPES) and Coastal Socio-Ecological Millenium Institute (SECOS), Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile

4 Centro Basal COPAS COASTAL, Universidad de Concepción

5 Biodiversity, Ecology and Evolution Dept., Complutense University of Madrid, Spain

* Corresponding author: a.a.h.genin@uu.nl

We parameterized the model using surveys, observations, and empirical experiments made between 1999 and 2015. Most model parameters were estimated by fitting the expected temporal trends from model dynamics to the field observations.

Equivalence between empirical changes in covers and model quantities

A stochastic cellular automaton is defined by the probabilities of switching states per time unit (one week) of the individual cells of a 2D grid. For example, in our model, the probability that a bare cell i switches to a coral cell per time unit, $P_i(b \rightarrow c)$, is defined by the following relationship:

$$P_i(b \rightarrow c) = r_c(1 + d_0 q_c)$$

where r_c quantifies the arrival of coral propagules to that cell, d_0 is the coral local effect (positive, zero, or negative), and q_c is the local cover of coral (proportion of neighbors of the focal cell in the “coral” state). The probability of switching states depends on the identity of the cell, hence the subscript i , because cells do not share the same neighborhood (in the above formula, q_c implicitly changes depending on which cell is considered in the landscape).

The change in the number of cells in a given state during a time step is equal to the difference between the number of cells entering and leaving that state. We can write this statement more formally. Taking the coral state as example, the expected change in the number of cells in the coral state $d n_c$ during a time step $d t$ is equal to:

$$\frac{d n_c}{d t} = \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{b,i} P_i(b \rightarrow c) - \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{c,i} P_i(c \rightarrow b)$$

where n_c is the number of cells in in the coral state, n_b the number of cells in the bare state, and n is the total number of cells. $\delta_{b,i}$ and $\delta_{c,i}$ are 1 if the cell i is in the bare or coral state, respectively, and 0 otherwise (thus, the two sums in the above formula have n_c and n_b non-zero terms). We can rework this relationship as follows by dividing all terms by n , and reworking the individuals sums to show n_b and n_c , the numbers of bare and corals cells:

$$\frac{d n_c}{n d t} = \frac{n_b}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{b,i} \frac{P_i(b \rightarrow c)}{n_b} - \frac{n_c}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{c,i} \frac{P_i(c \rightarrow b)}{n_c}$$

n_c/n and n_b/n are by definition the proportion of cells in the coral state and bare state in the cellular automaton, which can be written ρ_c and ρ_b following the terminology in the main text. The sums in the above relationship are effectively the average probabilities of bare cells to switch to the coral state, and vice versa, that we rewrite as $\langle P(b \rightarrow c) \rangle$ and $\langle P(c \rightarrow b) \rangle$. This yields the following equation:

$$\frac{d\rho_c}{dt} = \rho_b \langle P(b \rightarrow c) \rangle - \rho_c \langle P(c \rightarrow b) \rangle$$

where ρ_b and ρ_c are the proportions of cells in the bare and coral state.

A given site (area of $10 \times 10 \text{ m}^2$ to $20 \times 20 \text{ m}^2$) is represented by the whole 2D grid of the cellular automaton, while cells represent a small area ($10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$ to $20 \times 20 \text{ cm}^2$). Cell size is often not defined explicitly in a cellular automaton, but typically represents a small square area of edge length equal 1/100 to 1/1000 of the full 2D grid. This size determines how different ecological processes will be represented by the model. Here we consider it to be close to 20 cm, so that the lateral expansion of coral colonies is captured by the expansion of corals into their neighboring cells (similar to (Muthukrishnan et al. 2016), but different from Mumby *et al.* (2006) in which coral colonies always grow within one cell). Experimental work typically measures changes in covers in several small areas (quadrats) spread out within a given site, whose scales are equivalent to that of cells in the cellular automaton – in our case experiments were done based on $20 \times 20 \text{ cm}$ quadrats. In model terms, empirical measurements can be considered to describe the changes in cover of several selected cells within the full 2D grid of the model.

Continuing our coral example, if we consider a subset C of cells in the 2D grid, the expected change in the number of coral cells in that subset, dC/dt , is equal to:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = B \langle P(b \rightarrow c) \rangle - C \langle P(c \rightarrow b) \rangle$$

where C and B are the proportion of coral and bare cells in the subset of cells considered, $\langle P(b \rightarrow c) \rangle$ and $\langle P(c \rightarrow b) \rangle$ are the average probabilities of switching states for the subset of cells. Note that this relationship only describes the *expected* change in the number of corals cells, as the model is stochastic.

Experiments allow fixing the environmental conditions in which quadrats are placed, in particular their spatial neighborhood, so in model terms, this means that in an experimental setup, $P(b \rightarrow c)$ and

$P(c \rightarrow b)$ do not depend on the identity of the cell considered, but are effectively equal for all considered cells. This means that for a subset of cells set in specific experimental conditions with similar neighborhoods, $P(b \rightarrow c)$ and $P(c \rightarrow b)$ are constant, thus:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = B P(b \rightarrow c) - C P(c \rightarrow b)$$

The above relationship, can be rewritten using the explicit definitions for $P(b \rightarrow c)$ and $P(c \rightarrow b)$:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = B r_c (1 + d_0 q_c) - C m_c \text{ (equation 1)}$$

where r_c , d_0 and m_c are model parameters and q_c is the local coral cover around the subset of cells considered.

Experimental or observational work typically estimates average changes in covers over time, which corresponds to the quantity dC/dt in the model. Equation 1 thus provides a direct link between the model framework and parameters and experimental results measuring changes in covers, and can be solved analytically in many cases.

It is important to note that in the model world of a cellular automaton, only discrete changes within each cell can occur (e.g. going from 0% to 100% coral), while in reality, continuous changes in covers are measured. However, the above relationship links the *expected* change in coral cover in a subset of cells, which itself can be anywhere between 0 and 100%, to the measured empirical changes in cover.

Using the same reasoning, we can derive a similar relationship for changes in algal cover:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = B P(b \rightarrow a) - A P(a \rightarrow b)$$

which, written fully is equivalent to:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = B \left(r_a (\alpha + (1 - \alpha) \rho_a) + l_a q_a \right) - A \left(m_a + h_u g (\theta_c q_c + \theta_b q_b) \right) \text{ (equation 2)}$$

We used the equivalence offered by equation 1 and 2 between model parameters and empirical results to set most model parameter values.

Algal baseline mortality

The mortality of algae can be considered to occur through three different processes (i) herbivory by urchins, (ii) herbivory by fish, and (iii) remaining sources of algal mortality. We discuss (i) and (ii) explicitly in the section “Grazing of algae” further down, and focus on (iii) below.

The remaining mortality component is likely to be very low outside of specific algal mortality events (e.g. disease outbreaks), to the extent that in previous model work on coral-algal transitions, this base mortality of algae has been sometimes omitted from the model (e.g. Fung *et al.* 2011; Muthukrishnan *et al.* 2016). In our model, we preferred including a base mortality rate, which although very low, allows the creation of openings (bare cells) in a landscape that would be fully-colonized by algae. In the absence of such mortality, a landscape fully covered in algae is an absorbing state, out of which no recovery is possible, which can be considered unrealistic.

We used an estimate of algal mortality rate m_a from survival curves of *Lobophora variegata* (one of the main algae species at Rapa Nui) described in de Ruyter (1987), which measured the half lives t_{50} of algal blades without herbivory of 37, 44, 103, and 170 days. We converted these durations in weeks, and used the conversion relationship between half-lives and rates ($rate = \ln(2)/t_{50}$) to obtain a rate of $0.079 \pm 0.049 \text{ .wk}^{-1}$ (mean \pm s.d.).

Algal growth and recruitment

The estimation of most model parameters were based on an exclusion experiment conducted at “sitio Experimental” (coord. 27.135, -109.432) during October 2014 and December 2016, which involved clearing all coral and algae out of 5 small 20x20 cm quadrats, thus converting them to a 100% rocky area (equivalent to a ‘bare’ area in model terms), and controlling herbivore access during recolonization. We only used the initial part of this experiment (Oct 2014 to May 2015). After being cleared devoid of any coral or algae, each quadrat was put in one of the following conditions: (i) presence of urchins + fish, (ii) presence of fish only, (iii) presence of urchins only, or (iv) absence of any herbivore. The quadrats were set in 1.5x1.5 m areas cleared of corals and algae at the beginning of the experiment, so that the recolonization rate was influenced as little as possible by the algae or coral directly in the neighborhood. The increase in covers of algae and coral (if any) in the cleared 20x20 cm quadrats was then assessed during the weeks following the clearing.

To determine the model parameters related to the multiplication of algae, we considered the changes in algal cover in the absence of any herbivores (no fish nor urchins, $h_u=0$). The quadrats were not placed near existing patches of algae ($q_a \approx 0$) so that algal growth can be assumed to occur mostly from propagules (spores, seeds) in the water column and not lateral expansion.

In those conditions, the temporal dynamics of algae (equation 2) simplify into the following relationship:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = B r_a (\alpha + (1 - \alpha) \rho_a) - A m_a$$

where ρ_a is the average measured cover of algae at the experimental site. α represents, out of the all propagules from the water column, the fraction coming from outside the site relative to those from inside the site. A fully-closed site, with no exchange with the exterior, would have $\alpha=0$, while a completely open one, in which all propagules are external, would have $\alpha=1$. Because algae produce spores that are immediately viable, and most algae at Rapa Nui have a low height, we expect most propagules to originate from the site (Gaylord et al. 2002), so we used $\alpha=0.01$. In practice, the ratio α will depend of the oceanographic context of each site, determined by advection and “openness” of the site.

Since coral was absent from the experimental plots during the whole experiment ($C=0$), and that the total covers of algae, bare and coral sum to one ($A+B+C=1$), this means that we have $B=1-A$, and the above equation can be written as:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = r_a (\alpha + (1 - \alpha) \rho_a) - A (m_a + r_a (\alpha + (1 - \alpha) \rho_a))$$

Whose solution is the following, after defining $r'_a = r_a (\alpha + (1 - \alpha) \rho_a)$:

$$A(t) = A(0) e^{-r'_a t} + \frac{r'_a}{r'_a + m_a} (1 - e^{-(r'_a + m_a)t})$$

ρ_a here is the measured average cover of algae at the experimental site, 0.105 (i.e 10.5%), which was estimated from the measurement of algal covers in all experimental quadrats before intervention. m_a is the base mortality rate for algae defined above (section “Algal baseline mortality”) and is equal to 0.079 .wk⁻¹. We adjusted the above function to the trend in regrowth during the experiment (blue line,

Figure S1.1) using least-square estimation, to obtain an estimate for r_a of $1.81 \pm 1.00 \text{ .wk}^{-1}$ (mean \pm s.d). We thus used the average $r_a = 1.81 \text{ .wk}^{-1}$ for model simulations (and α assumed as 0.01 as stated above).

Figure S1.1 Change in algal cover during the exclusion experiment in the absence of any herbivores. The cover of algae before removal (left of vertical line) is given by the leftmost set of points, then drops down close to zero at the date of removal (2014-11-20), then grows back up in the weeks after the removal (rightmost set of points). The shape of the point indicates the experimental replicate.

l_a was estimated based on clearing small 20x20 cm areas within large algal patches (Figure S1.2) and quantifying the regrowth of the existing algae (mainly *Lobophora variegata*). Under such conditions, we assumed that regrowth occurred mostly through the lateral expansion of existing algae, or through very-short distance dispersal of propagules, both processes being captured by the coefficient l_a . In model terms, this means we considered the quantity $r_a(\alpha + (1 - \alpha)\rho_a)$ to be negligible before $l_a q_a$ in the experimental conditions. We assumed $q_a = 1$ since all sides of the cleared quadrats are covered in algae, which implies $q_b = q_c = 0$. In those conditions, we have from equation 2:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = B l_a - A m_a$$

As coral was not present at any time of the experiment, we have $B = 1 - A$ and the above equation can be simplified and solved into the following solution:

$$A(t) = A(0)e^{-(l_a+m_a)t} + \frac{l_a}{l_a+m_a}(1 - e^{-(l_a+m_a)t})$$

which allows estimating the value of l_a by regressing the temporal trends against the observed data, using non-linear least square (Figure S1.3). This yielded an estimate for l_a of $3.0 \cdot 10^{-2} \pm 1.3 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ wk}^{-1}$ (mean \pm standard deviation), and we thus used the average $3.0 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ wk}^{-1}$ for l_a in model simulations.

Figure S1.2 Picture of a 20x20 cm quadrat cleared within an algal patch (site Kaviti, October 2013) to estimate lateral expansion of algae. In this picture, most of the cover of the algal mat is made by *Lobophora variegata*.

Figure S1.3 Visually-estimated cover of algae in the 20x20 cm quadrat, used to determine the average algal growth rate per week (model prediction in blue lines). Dates on the x-axis are given as Year-Month.

It is worthy of note that the above determination of rates for algae does not take into account interspecific variability. For example, filamentous algae may have a higher reproduction rate than foliose algae (e.g. *Lobophora variegata*). However, those experiment capture well enough the relative differences in coral and algal ecological rates to investigate qualitatively their self-organization before

transitions.

Coral recruitment

We recall that the multiplication of corals occurs through the following relationship, where $P(b \rightarrow c)$ describes the probability of a cell in the bare state to switch to the coral state:

$$P(b \rightarrow c) = r_c (1 + d_0 q_c)$$

Here, r_c describes the increase in coral cover on bare surfaces due to the advection, and growth into adult corals of propagules (larvae) from the water column. d_0 describes the effect of corals on the increase in coral cover in their local neighborhood (local feedback), relative to the homogeneous recruitment captured by r_c . d_0 can be neutral ($d_0=0$), positive ($d_0>0$) or negative ($d_0<0$).

A positive d_0 indicates that the increase in coral cover is higher around established corals because of one or more ecological processes, for example because of corals expanding laterally (reef-building), regrowing from broken off coral fragments, or favoring locally the recruitment and survival of coral recruits (e.g. by providing crevices/refuges). A negative d_0 would represent a situation where coral cover is slowed around established colonies relative to further away from them, for example because of direct, negative contact interactions (Idjadi and Karlson 2007) or predation of larvae (Fabricius and Metzner 2004). A value of d_0 close or equal to zero would indicate a situation in which established colonies have little to no effect on the increase in coral cover in their surroundings. It is important to note that all these processes can occur at the same time (e.g. coral could expand laterally, but also compete with neighbors): d_0 captures the net effect of their combination.

The coral species making most of the abundance at Rapa-Nui (mainly *Porites lobata* and *Pocillopora verrucosa*) show little tall reef-building in that environment, but do expand laterally, which would contribute to a positive d_0 for this species. There is evidence for negative contact coral-coral interactions (Idjadi and Karlson 2007) for at least one of the species (*Porites lobata*) present at Rapa Nui, so d_0 may also be lowered in some circumstances, as the survival of colonies with neighbors may be lower. However, we generally expect the coral communities of Rapa Nui to be best modelled by a positive d_0 , mainly because we expect the lateral expansion of *P. lobata* to be the dominant driver of coral cover around established colonies. However, this may not be true for all reefs or all coral species, so to better reflect the range of possible patterns, we explored different values for d_0 (-1, -0.5, 0, +0.5

and +8) to reflect qualitatively different behaviors, and make model results more generalizable in other environments. A value of -1 means that a cell in the bare state will not become colonized by corals if all of its neighbors are in the coral state ($q_c=1$) – this would represent very strong competition between neighboring colonies, which although unrealistic, is useful to fully examine the model behavior. A more realistic example of competition is given by $d_0=-0.5$ (coral growth is halved when all the neighbors of a cell are in the coral state), which corresponds approximately to the reduction in growth rate of *Pocillopora verrucosa* with neighbors reported experimentally in (Evensen et al. 2021). A value of $d_0=0$ represents no net effect of coral colonies on their neighborhood, which may be relevant for *Pocillopora verrucosa* present at Rapa Nui, which produce small colonies that do not reach large sizes and appear haphazardly-distributed in space. Finally, we chose a value that represented species which are able to grow laterally, which would correspond most to *P. lobata* at Rapa Nui. There is considerable variation in existing models in the relative order of magnitude given to coral growth relative to the increase in coral cover due to recruitment: (Fung et al. 2011) considers lateral growth to increase coral cover 20 times as fast than recruitment of spawning corals; (Mumby et al. 2006) includes a lateral expansion rate of 0.8 cm.yr^{-1} , which would correspond to a time of eight years to cover 50% of a $20 \times 20 \text{ cm}$ plot located near an existing colony, and corresponds to a rate of 0.00154 .wk^{-1} ($(0.8 / 10) / 52$), *i.e.* $d_0 \sim 0.2$ (using our value for r_c). Muthukrishnan *et al.* (2016) a very large difference in probability of two order of magnitudes, as the probability of recruiting next to corals is approximately 10^{-2} , and that of recruiting from propagules around 10^{-4} . Thus, the scaling of growth relative to recruitment appears to depend on the particular model considerations and assumptions, so in such absence of clear consensus, we consider two cases, a small value of $d_0=0.5$, and a larger value of $d_0=8$, to capture a range of possible values.

Those values thus represent different cases that aim at illustrating model behavior and are consistent with the species observed in our model system, however, we stress that the exact values for d_0 are unknown in reality, and are likely to vary depending on the coral species considered and environmental conditions.

We used results from the exclusion experiment mentioned above to estimate the other parameters related to coral dynamics. We focused on the experimental conditions that were found to be most favorable to coral (*i.e.* with urchins and fish), and starting from experimental conditions in which the substrate had been cleared of coral and algae. Quadrats were placed in $1.5 \times 1.5 \text{ m}$ plots cleared of

corals and algae prior to the experiment. In those conditions, there was no colonization due to lateral expansion of existing corals. Because of the clearing, although small in extent, the influence of neighbors was reduced. In those conditions, we assumed that the product $d_0 q_c$ was positive and much lower than one and could be neglected. In those conditions, the observed change in coral cover is equal to the following (by simplifying equation 1):

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = B r_c - C m_c$$

During the whole experiment, in the aforementioned experimental conditions, the cover of algae was relatively low at all times (on average 5%), so we assumed $A \approx 0$. With such assumption, we have $C = 1 - B$ (because the sum of covers $A + B + C$ is equal to 1), and the above equation has the following solution:

$$C(t) = C(0) e^{-(r_c + m_c)t} + \frac{r_c}{r_c + m_c} (1 - e^{-(r_c + m_c)t})$$

Coral baseline mortality m_c is very low (outside of specific mortality events, which did not occur during the weeks of the experiment), so we neglected its value before r_c in the above equation. As a result, the above equation can be simplified into:

$$C(t) = (C(0) - 1) e^{-r_c t} + 1$$

We fitted this function to the empirical recovery of coral after removal, using least square estimation (Figure S1.4). This yielded a value of $1.31 \cdot 10^{-3} \pm 2.92 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ wk}^{-1}$ for r_c . We thus used the value $r_c = 1.31 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ wk}^{-1}$ for model simulations.

It is important to highlight the limits of this small experiment. Recruitment is highly stochastic and depends on the specific oceanographic conditions at the experimental site, so we need to stress that the value we obtained here most likely depends on the particular environmental conditions during which the experiment was carried out. In addition, it appeared that the removal treatment left some of the established coral (Replicate 4, Figure S1.4), which, although coral cover appeared to drop to zero for all replicates, could have contributed to a faster increase of cover during the subsequent months.

Despite these caveats, we found the rate r_c to be within the order of magnitudes of other modelling work (e.g. Fung et al. 2011, reported rates between $9.6 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ wk}^{-1}$ and $1.9 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ wk}^{-1}$; Mumby et al. 2006,

reported rates of $1.9 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ wk}^{-1}$ for spawning corals). A higher or lower recruitment rate would not change the general trends in spatial patterns observed before shifts in coral cover, but would change the stress levels at which they occur.

Figure S1.4 Change in coral cover during the exclusion experiment in the presence of urchins and fish. The cover of coral before removal (left of vertical line) is given by the leftmost set of points, then drops down close to zero at the date of removal (2014-12-03), then grows back up in the months after the removal (rightmost set of points). Note that the removal was sometimes reported as incomplete, i.e. a few percent of coral covers appeared to be left on the day of the removal.

It is important to note that the increase in cover captured by r_c takes into account the mortality in corals occurring between the recruit and adult stage (at which a coral has a size comparable to that represented by a grid cell, i.e. approx. 400 cm^2 , and escapes early mortality). Consumption of recruits or juvenile coral (e.g. by urchins or fish) is thus included by the coefficient r_c , and m_c describes the mortality of established adult corals.

Algal mortality and grazing

The mortality of algae occurs through the following probability:

$$P(a \rightarrow b) = m_a + h_u g(\theta_b q_b + \theta_c q_c)$$

where m_a represents the base mortality rate of algae, and the product $h_u g(\theta_b q_b + \theta_c q_c)$ quantifies the mortality due to grazing.

In the latter expression, h_u represents the average biomass of urchins per area ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$). θ_b and θ_c quantify the relative preference of urchins for bare areas (rock, sand) and coral patches relative to the average density at the site. These values are above one when urchins prefer a specific habitat type, and below one if they appear to avoid those areas. For example, if h_u is $0.8 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$ and θ_c is 1.5, then we expect the effective density of urchin biomass in coral patches to be $0.8 \times 1.5 = 1.2 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$. The product $h_u(\theta_b q_b + \theta_c q_c)$ thus represents the quantity of urchins per area around the focal cell, depending on the local covers of bare area q_b and coral q_c . This quantity is then multiplied by g , which quantifies the grazing rate of urchins, in $\text{m}^2\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, to obtain the effective reduction rate in algal cover per time step due to herbivory.

We estimated θ_b and θ_c using surveys directed towards the estimation of urchin abundances. These surveys were based on regularly-spaced $1 \times 1 \text{ m}$ or $50 \times 50 \text{ cm}$ quadrats along transects which the number and life stage (adult, juvenile, recruit) of urchins were recorded, along with a simplified description of the microhabitat present in the quadrat (algae, coral, or rock). Those surveys were done between 2013 and 2019, totalling 23 surveys at 13 sites, which overall captured the diversity of seascapes encountered at Rapa Nui.

We extracted from the surveys the average density of adult, juvenile or “recruit” urchin in each microhabitat. We converted this density (in individuals/area) into biomass per area using the average size of each urchin life stage, and a previously-established size-weight relationship based on 68 individuals ($\ln(\text{mass}) = -0.54 + 2.88 \ln(\text{diameter})$, with size in centimeters and mass in grams). This allowed us to get an estimate of the average urchin biomass in bare areas, d_b (for bare areas) and d_c (for coral patches). We then computed the average biomass per area d across all microhabitat types. By definition of θ_b and θ_c , we could thus get estimates as $\theta_b = d_b/d$ and $\theta_c = d_c/d$ for each of the 23 surveys. We obtained $\theta_b = 1.03 \pm 0.12$ and $\theta_c = 0.96 \pm 0.29$ (means \pm s.d.; Figure S1.5).

We considered that grazing was negligible within algal patches. This is an important characteristic of the model, and matches observations made in the field, as (i) urchins (*Diadema savignyi*) are very rarely found in algal patches a) and (ii) when put inside an algal patch, urchins will move away from it (E. Wieters, *personal obs.*). It is also important to note that we did not consider grazing by herbivorous fish, since fish stocks at Rapa Nui have been very depleted and most likely do not constitute a strong driver of coral and algal abundance for the time period we are considering (~ 2000 -2020). This

assumption matches experimental results, as the grazing of algae was not significantly higher in the presence of fish than in their absence (Figure S1.6, a).

Figure S1.5 (a) Average biomass density of urchins in bare and coral patches and (b) distributions of the corresponding microhabitat preferences θ_b (for bare areas), and θ_c (for coral patches).

g was estimated from the previously-mentioned exclusion experiment (see “Algal growth and recruitment” section). We contrasted two experimental treatments, one with urchins and the other without urchins. In the latter case, cages had been put to exclude herbivores from accessing the small surface – in the herbivore exclusion treatment, we thus have $h_u=0$. We recall that in the experimental conditions, the nearby corals were cleared (in a 1.5 x 1.5 m area), so we took the simplifying assumption that $q_c \approx 0$. This is an assumption as the clearing is relatively minor in spatial extent, so nearby corals, although at least one meter away from the experimental quadrat, could still influence grazer behavior. However, given the similarity in values of θ_b and θ_c , this assumption has a minor effect on parameter estimation. Under such conditions, the measured changes in algal cover $dA_{herbivory}$ and $dA_{no\ herbivory}$ are thus equal to:

$$\left(\frac{dA}{dt}\right)_{herbivory} = r_a(\alpha + (1-\alpha)\rho_a) - m_a - h_u g \theta_b q_b$$

$$\left(\frac{dA}{dt}\right)_{no\ herbivory} = r_a(\alpha + (1-\alpha)\rho_a) - m_a$$

Calling D the difference in the cover measured between the two treatments ($A_{no\ herbivory} - A_{herbivory}$), its

change over time is given by $\left(\frac{dA}{dt}\right)_{no\ herbivory} - \left(\frac{dA}{dt}\right)_{herbivory}$ which is:

$$\frac{dD}{dt} = h_u g \theta_b$$

as $q_a = 0$, $q_c \approx 0$ and $q_b = 1 - q_a - q_c$. The explicit solution of the above equation is:

$$D(t) = D(0) + h_u g \theta_b t$$

h_u at the experimental site during the experiment was estimated to be 0.39 kg.m^{-2} , which was done by estimating urchin density in five 1.5 m^2 quadrats overlapping the experimental plots, and converting densities into biomasses using the average weight of adult and juvenile urchins. θ_b was estimated above as 1.03. The remaining parameter in the above equation, g , was estimated using least-square estimation. For each experimental replicate, we computed the differences in algal cover with and without urchins $D(t)$, both in presence and absence of fish (Figure S1.6). This yielded an estimate of $0.19 \pm 0.24 \text{ .wk}^{-1}.\text{kg}^{-1}.\text{m}^2$ for g (mean \pm s.d.). We thus used the average value 0.19 in model simulations for g .

Figure S1.6 (a) Changes in algal cover over time for different combinations of potential herbivores, with or without urchins (+U and -U) and fish (+F and -F). Significant differences ($P < 0.10$) of a between treatments are highlighted by the stars and arrows above the graph. (b) Differences between treatments with and without

urchins over time, in the presence (red) or absence of fish (blue). Lines indicate the trajectory for each replicate (10 in total). The fitted increase in algal cover following removal is represented by the blue line, with the ribbon indicating the standard error.

It is important to note that the current formulation of the model assumes that the grazing rate of urchins is constant regardless of the urchin density and the covers of coral and algae in the landscape. There is evidence supporting the density-dependence in the grazing rate of urchins, in particular where high densities can produce a change in urchin behavior and the opening of barren grounds, and may be another source of positive feedback underpinning abrupt transitions (Ling et al. 2014). A natural extension of the model could be to include such density-dependent grazer behavior.

Coral mortality

Because the base coral mortality m_c was a variable representing a stressor in our set of simulations, we did not use experiments to set a specific value, but worked on a range of values that were found to cover the full range of model behavior (*i.e.* from going all the way from low mortality rates which allowed high coral covers, to high mortality rates for which coral cover was zero). Once this range of values were set, we chose values for m_c for which the coral cover was high to use in simulations sets where m_c was fixed (*i.e.* along decreases in herbivores or increase in the frequency of mortality events), see Figure 2 in Main Text.

The mortality rate occurring during mortality events (e.g. bleaching events), m_e , was set based on the 2000 March-April mass bleaching event that occurred at Rapa Nui. This event produced a reduction in live coral cover reported to be up to 85% in 10 weeks (Wellington, 2001; in shallow waters). The impact appeared to be less severe when considering depths between 3 and 20 m (Figure S1.7; (Wieters et al. 2014), on average 61 ± 7.9 % (mean \pm s.d.). In such short time period, we considered the effect of recruitment and baseline mortality to be negligible. The observed change in cover during that event is thus:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -m_e C$$

whose solution is

$$C(t) = C(0)e^{-m_e t}$$

We observed decreases in coral cover of 66, 65 and 52 % for the three sites documented between 1999 and 2000 (Figure S1.5). Calling the percent mortality M_c , and considering that it occurred in ten weeks, we have $C(10) = (1 - M_c)C(0)$, from which we can deduce m_c from the previous equation, as

$$m_c = \frac{-\log(C(10)/C(0))}{10} = \frac{-\log(1 - M_c)}{10}$$

which yields an estimate for m_c of $0.095 \pm 0.019 \text{ wk}^{-1}$ (mean \pm s.d.).

Figure S1.7 Average coral cover before (year 1999) and right after (year 2000) the bleaching event at Rapa Nui for the three sites surveyed on those years, based on photoquadrats with an approximate area of 50x50 cm.

References

- Evensen, N. R., Y.-M. Bozec, P. J. Edmunds, and P. J. Mumby. 2021. Scaling the effects of ocean acidification on coral growth and coral–coral competition on coral community recovery. *PeerJ* 9:e11608.
- Fabricius, K. E., and J. Metzner. 2004. Scleractinian walls of mouths: Predation on coral larvae by corals. *Coral Reefs* 23.
- Fung, T., R. M. Seymour, and C. R. Johnson. 2011. Alternative stable states and phase shifts in coral reefs under anthropogenic stress. *Ecology* 92:967–982.
- Gaylord, B., D. C. Reed, P. T. Raimondi, L. Washburn, and S. R. McLean. 2002. A physically-based model of macroalgal spore dispersal in the wave and current-dominated nearshore. *Ecology* 83:1239–1251.
- Idjadi, J. A., and R. H. Karlson. 2007. Spatial Arrangement of Competitors Influences Coexistence of Reef-building Corals. *Ecology* 88:2449–2454.
- Ling, S. D., R. E. Scheibling, A. Rassweiler, C. R. Johnson, N. Shears, S. D. Connell, A. K. Salomon, et al. 2014. Global regime shift dynamics of catastrophic sea urchin overgrazing. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 370:20130269–20130269.
- Mumby, P. J., J. D. Hedley, K. Zychaluk, A. R. Harborne, and P. G. Blackwell. 2006. Revisiting the catastrophic die-off of the urchin *Diadema antillarum* on Caribbean coral reefs: Fresh insights on resilience from a simulation model. *Ecological Modelling* 196:131–148.
- Muthukrishnan, R., J. O. Lloyd-Smith, and P. Fong. 2016. Mechanisms of resilience: empirically quantified positive feedbacks produce alternate stable states dynamics in a model of a tropical reef. (B. Silliman, ed.) *Journal of Ecology* 104:1662–1672.
- Wieters, E. A., A. Medrano, and A. Perez Matus. 2014. Functional community structure of shallow hard bottom communities at Easter Island (Rapa Nui). *Latin American Journal of Aquatic Research* 42:827–844.